

Endoscopic Stereo Vision for Robotic 3D Detection of Thin Wire Features

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Abstract—Vision systems are more and more employed in robotic applications to perceive the surrounding environment and to make decisions accordingly. Despite this, the 3D reconstruction is a non-trivial problem for thin deformable linear objects. The cameras on the market that allow the 3D modelling of very small objects are bulky and expensive, and as a consequence cannot be easily integrated with a robotic system. This paper proposes a stereo vision system completely integrable into the robot end-effector, composed of two low-cost off-the-shelf endoscopic cameras with the aim of detecting tiny wires in the scene and identifying their location and diameter. The proposed method splices state-of-the-art vision algorithms applied to macro cameras obtaining, for wires with a diameter of few millimeters or less than a millimeter, a diameter estimation error lower than 10% and a location estimation error lower than 3%. The presented approach can be generalized to different types of endoscopic cameras and thin target objects.

I. INTRODUCTION

Managing deformable linear objects (DLOs) is a complex task for a robot. The DLOs are those objects that have one dimension significantly bigger than the other two, such as wires, cables, tubes, and medical hoses. Given the great variety of these objects, and the fact that they can have very small diameters, even less than a millimeter, it's challenging to reconstruct their shape and 3D features with standard vision systems. In this paper, the problem of the position and diameter estimation of thin DLOs by means of the 3D reconstruction is tackled using a stereo vision approach, by exploiting endoscopic cameras. Standard depth cameras like Intel Realsense, Microsoft Kinect or PMD Camboard Pico Flexx fail in recognize very thin wires [1]. Other devices, like Zivid One+, IDS Ensenso X36 or Photoneo PhoXi can reach sub-millimeter accuracy in 3D reconstruction so they can be used successfully when dealing with wires that have a diameter of less than a millimeter or a few millimeters. However, the latter are too expensive for standard robotic systems, and bulky for the integration on the robot end-effector, by limiting their use in case of narrow manipulation spaces. To overcome these problems, a setup consisting of two off-the-shelf endoscopic macro cameras assembled on the robot fingertip is proposed. These devices allow to have good resolution at close range which is useful when dealing with thin DLOs and in narrow spaces. The 3D reconstruction of tiny objects in small working areas is an

open research problem and several researchers are working in this field to develop innovative solutions. De Gregorio et al. [2] proposed a stereo vision approach based on a single 2D camera, mounted on a robotic arm to gather multiple views, by maintaining a small size for the whole vision system. This approach allows to have multiple baselines, obtaining good results for small objects. Braun Neto et al. [3] presented a low-cost 3D scanning system using a Light Detecting and Ranging device to scan an object and generate a CAD file with a reconstruction algorithm. In [4] the stereo vision technique is used to define and measure an object's volume, dealing with different sizes. Harjoko et al. [5] developed a rotating platform to acquire different views of a small object in order to reconstruct it in 3D. A very active field of research concerns the manipulation of DLOs and their shape reconstruction using computer vision techniques. Caporali et al. [6] used a 2D camera mounted on a robotic arm to detect thin wires. The robotic arm allows to reconstruct the 3D scene from multiple views and the thin wires are modelled with a B-spline. Cirillo et al. [7] studied a technique to extract pixels corresponding to the wire from a 2D image and find a label on them using machine learning, then, exploiting stereo vision, the wire is inserted in a switchgear with the label oriented facing up. However, for almost all these solutions the calibration is more laborious and the time needed for image acquisition and processing for 3D reconstruction is longer. In other kinds of applications, the DLOs can have connectors at their end, so some researchers, such as Monguzzi et al. [8], proposed vision-based strategy that classifies the connectors and their state (free or occluded), and estimates their pose. Other researchers used the combination of tactile sensor data and machine learning techniques to detect the wire diameter [9] for the following manipulation. Also in these cases, the estimation of some features for thin wires represents the main objective (e.g., wire diameter, wire end).

The main contribution of this paper is the development of a vision system (both from hardware and software point of view) based on a couple of low-cost endoscopic macro cameras to estimate the location and the diameter of thin wires (the diameters of considered wires range from 0.5 mm to 4 mm). Furthermore, from the reconstructed 3D scene, the point cloud can be segmented into clusters in order to detect the wires, their centres and their orientations. The proposed approach exploits the techniques illustrated in [10]–[13], suitably adapted to the images acquired from the endoscopic cameras, for the calibration, the disparity map computation,

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Fig. 1. Stereo system and Σ_c camera frame.

and the region of interest selection. Additionally, the acquired images can be used to find the boundaries of the wire by using edge detection techniques and to compute the diameter by exploiting the distance of the wire from the camera obtained with the previous 3D reconstruction. Finally, to validate the 3D points returned from the image elaboration, the wires are picked from a warehouse by means of fingers developed by some of the authors in [14], sensorized with tactile sensors exploited to evaluate the correct wire grasp. The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section II explains the methodology proposed to calibrate the stereo vision system, reconstruct the 3D scene and detect the DLOs diameters. Section III, first, gives an overview of the hardware setup used within this paper, then, the methodology is evaluated. Finally, Sec. IV, concludes the paper.

II. METHODOLOGY

The objective is to propose a methodology for the position estimation of wires stored in a warehouse and the detection of their diameters (considered values range from 0.5 mm to 4 mm), based on the stereo vision, in order to grasp the correct wire selected on the basis of estimated diameter. First, the cameras need to be calibrated, then they can be used for the 3D scene reconstruction and the diameter detection.

A. Calibration

The stereo camera calibration aims to estimate the intrinsic and extrinsic parameters of each camera and the inter-camera geometry. The intrinsic parameters are for example the focal length, the optical centre, and the skew coefficient, while the extrinsic parameters give information about the rotation and translation of each camera relative to the calibration pattern; finally, the inter-camera geometry consists of the translation and rotation between the two cameras in the stereo pair together with the fundamental matrix and the essential matrix. The cameras are arranged in a generic relative pose, as schematized in Fig. 1, and the Σ_c stereo system frame is fixed in the principal point of the camera 1. The cameras are modelled through a pinhole camera model, hence the relation between the 3D point $[x y z]^T$ and its image projection $[u v]^T$ is given by [10]

$$s \begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{A} [\mathbf{R} \quad \mathbf{t}] \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \text{with} \quad \mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha & \gamma & u_0 \\ 0 & \beta & v_0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where s is an arbitrary scale factor, \mathbf{A} is the camera intrinsic matrix, with (u_0, v_0) the principal point in pixels, γ the

factor that takes into account the skew of the two image axes, α and β the focal lengths along the u and v axes in pixels. Moreover, the world coordinate system and the camera coordinate system are related through the \mathbf{R} rotation matrix and the \mathbf{t} translation vector. The 3D points and their corresponding 2D image points are necessary to estimate camera parameters. These correspondences can be obtained using multiple images from different points of view of a calibration pattern, such as a custom pattern detector, an asymmetric circle grid, or a checkerboard. The latter is an alternation of black and white squares of equal size, and it requires to have no 180-degree ambiguity. The control points are the corners of the squares that can be detected on the 2D image automatically by using a corner detector algorithm. By positioning the origin in the lower-right corner point of the top-left square, it is possible to determine the coordinates of the points by using the checkerboard dimensions, in terms of the number of squares along the rows and the columns, and the checkerboard square size, that is fixed. The calibration algorithm first assumes the lens distortion equal to zero, and it finds a solution for the intrinsic and extrinsic parameters in closed form. Then, this solution is used to estimate all parameters including the distortion coefficients using nonlinear least-squares minimization. The calibration procedure is reported in the Fig. 2 and its accuracy is estimated by the mean reprojection error, which is a pixel-wise numeric value specifying the average Euclidean distance between detected and reprojected points.

B. 3D scene reconstruction

The intrinsic and extrinsic parameters as well as the inter-camera geometry are necessary to reconstruct the 3D scene. For this purpose, two necessary intermediate steps are the stereo images rectification and the disparity image computation. The rectification phase places the two scene images on a shared image plane on which the images are projected so as to the matching points have identical row coordinates. This perspective seems like the two cameras are parallel and has a twofold burden: to undistort, which means to remove the lens distortion, and to rectify the pair of images. The two

Fig. 2. Steps followed for the calibration procedure.

undistorted and rectified images are the input of the disparity map algorithm, which computes the displacement between corresponding pixels in the two images, by exploiting a *Semi-Global Matching* method. The latter needs to know the disparity range, composed of minimum and maximum disparity values that fill the whole horizontal variation between matching pixels, as well as the uniqueness threshold, which is the minimum value of uniqueness useful to mark the k estimated disparity value for a pixel as unreliable if the smallest Hamming distance over the whole disparity range is less than the uniqueness threshold multiplied by the Hamming distance corresponding to the k disparity value. The semi-global approach gets the matching cost matrix from the Hamming distance between corresponding pixels, which is computed from the Census transform of the two rectified images. Then, the method assigns to the pixel the disparity value that minimizes the cost. Finally, the just calculated disparity map is the sole required information by the 3D scene reconstruction algorithm, which returns the 3D points coordinates of the scene, corresponding to the pixels in the disparity image, with respect to the Σ_c frame. At this point, the 3D information is available and it can be elaborated to investigate the p_{ci} wire location with respect to the Σ_c frame and the θ_i wire orientation in the image plane, with $i = 1, \dots, n$, where n is the number of wires in the scene. Firstly, a Region Of Interest (ROI) is selected in the point cloud by a Kd-tree based search algorithm, a binary tree algorithm, one of the Nearest Neighbor Algorithms, that at each node splits the data points into two sets by following the median split criteria. Then, the selected point cloud is segmented into clusters on the basis of both a minimum Euclidean distance among points of different clusters and a minimum number of points in each group. The centre of the i -th cluster is computed as the mean of the points in it and these three coordinates represent the p_{ci} wire location with respect to the Σ_c frame. Concerning the θ_i wire orientation in the image plane, it is estimated as a first-order polynomial passing through two points computed as the mean of the cluster first half and second half along the y direction. Figure 3 shows a flowchart describing the 3D scene reconstruction algorithm.

C. Diameter detection

The 3D scene reconstruction is of paramount importance to discover the scene objects depth. The latter renders the estimated distance of the wire from the camera and it can be exploited not only for the wire picking but also for the computation of the wire diameter. In order to avoid errors due to the noisy point cloud, the diameter is computed from the 2D image with the information of the wire z coordinate. The wire is found in the 2D image through the p_{ci} point and, from there, the two edges are detected. The coordinates of the p_{ci} points are used to find the (u_{ci}, v_{ci}) centre of the wires in the 2D image, neglecting the skew ($\gamma = 0$), assuming the reference frame as the Σ_c camera frame ($\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{I}$, $\mathbf{t} = [0\ 0\ 0]^T$), and the image rectified ($\alpha = \beta = f$). Therefore,

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the 3D scene reconstruction algorithm.

considering s unitary, the Eq. (1) becomes

$$u = \frac{f}{z}x + u_0 \quad (2)$$

$$v = \frac{f}{z}y + v_0 \quad (3)$$

The wire in the image may not be completely vertical so the image is rotated according to θ_i for each processed wire, by obtaining the (u_r, v_r) rotated coordinates. The (u_{ci}, v_{ci}) pixel coordinates are mapped into the rotated image by applying the transformation in the two-dimensional plane

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_r \\ v_r \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{R}_{2D} \left(\begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \end{bmatrix} - \mathbf{c} \right) + \mathbf{c} \quad (4)$$

with

$$\mathbf{R}_{2D} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{c} is a two-element vector containing the coordinates of the image centre. The edges of the image are evaluated by using the *Sobel* gradient operator, obtaining a matrix with the same dimensions as the 2D image, containing 1 if there is an edge in that location, otherwise 0. Then, the edge image is explored along the v direction, selecting the row containing the pixel (u_{ci}, v_{ci}) , in order to find the edges closest to the centre of the wire. Once the u_{e1} and u_{e2} coordinates of the edges are located, the Eq. (2) is reversed to obtain the diameter in millimeters

$$d = \frac{z}{f}(u_{e2} - u_{e1}) \quad (6)$$

The pseudo-code Algorithm 1 summarizes the diameter computation procedure.

Algorithm 1 Diameter computation

Input: I 2D image, p_{ci}

```
for  $i = 0; i < \text{number of wires}; i++$  do
  Compute wire centre in  $I$   $\triangleright$  from Eqs. (2)–(3)
   $I_r \leftarrow \text{imrotate}(I, \theta_i)$ 
   $(u_{ci}, v_{ci}) \leftarrow \text{Remap image centre}$   $\triangleright$  from Eq. (4)
   $I_{edges} \leftarrow \text{edge}(I_r, \text{'Sobel'}, \text{threshold})$ 
   $I_{row} \leftarrow I_{edges}(v_{ci}, :)$ 
   $edges \leftarrow \text{find}(I_{row} == 1)$ 
   $u_{e1} \leftarrow \text{max}(edges(\text{find}(edges < u_{ci})))$ 
   $u_{e2} \leftarrow \text{min}(edges(\text{find}(edges > u_{ci})))$ 
  Compute  $d_i$   $\triangleright$  from Eq. (6)
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end forOutput: d

III. EXPERIMENTS

To validate the proposed methodology, a set of experiments is considered and a suitable setup is adopted. The latter consists of an UR5e robotic arm by Universal Robots equipped with a commercial Robotiq Hand-E parallel gripper and a couple of fingers that integrate tactile sensors onboard, custom-made by the authors, mounted on the gripper. Interested readers can find more information about the tactile sensor in [14]. The developed vision system involves two off-the-shelf endoscopic cameras, with a resolution of 640×480 pixels, that are locked in a suitably designed case, assembled on the rear side of one of the fingers (see Fig. 4). The proposed task involves the picking of the wires by the robot from the warehouse, selected on the basis of estimated diameter. The position of the warehouse with respect to the base of the robot is known but the wires are at a distance not known *a priori*. Therefore, the vision system provides information on the diameter of the wires and the distance along z with respect to the Σ_c camera frame in which they are positioned (see Fig. 5). The proposed diameter calculation technique is validated with four wires in the scene, while the grasping is executed by choosing among two wires. The calibration procedure reported in Sec. II-A is implemented in MATLAB, acquiring 13 pictures for each camera from different points of view by moving the robotic arm. The calibration pattern chosen is a checkerboard with

Fig. 4. Hardware setup.

Fig. 5. Wires arranged in the warehouse, top view (top) and lateral view (bottom).

6 rows and 11 columns and a square size equal to 2 mm, compatible with the dimensions of the objects of interest. These numbers result from a selection made through trial and error, obtaining a mean reprojection error equal to 0.27 pixels, and by taking into account the typical sizes of objects of interest. Once the stereo camera is calibrated, the diameter computation technique is tested by acquiring a couple of images with four wires of different diameters. Figure 6 shows the image from the camera 1 in the stereo system with the wires of diameter 2.15 mm, 0.50 mm, 1.20 mm, and 3.90 mm, from the left. The wires are positioned at different distance from the cameras, respectively 150.0 mm, 95.0 mm, 138.0 mm, 132.0 mm. The nominal diameters are measured using a vernier calliper with a resolution of 0.05 mm. The images are acquired at a distance from the wires in the range 90–140 mm, which is the focal range for the adopted cameras. The images are processed implementing the flowchart presented in Sec. II-B in MATLAB, for the rectification, the disparity map computation, and the 3D scene reconstruction. In particular, for the disparity map (see Fig. 7), a disparity

Fig. 6. Wires of different diameters, from the left: 2.15 mm, 0.50 mm, 1.20 mm, and 3.90 mm, at different distances from cameras.

Fig. 7. Disparity map for the four wires scene.

range equal to 30–94 pixels, and a uniqueness threshold equal to 40 are chosen. Then, a ROI is selected with a range in the z direction equal to 30–180 mm in order to eliminate possible background noise, and the wires are clustered using an Euclidean distance of 0.8 and a minimum number of points in the cluster equal to 3000 for the point cloud. For each cluster, the p_{ci} centre and the θ_i orientation are computed. Figure 8 shows the four clusters of different colors for each wire and the centres p_{ci} highlighted. In particular, the reconstructed wires distances from the cameras are respectively 148.7 mm, 95.7 mm, 139.7 mm and 135.3 mm, which correspond to the following percentage errors with respect to nominal distance reported above: 0.9%, 0.7%, 1.4% and 2.5%. Following the Algorithm 1, for each wire, the centre of the cluster is projected in the 2D image using the Eqs. (2–3) with f , u_0 and v_0 equal to 896.96, 309.21 and 220.43 pixels, respectively. The image is rotated of θ_i and the p_{ci} point is mapped in the rotated image, by considering the centre of the image with coordinates [258.5, 220.5], by applying the mapping

Fig. 8. Highlighted segmentation with wires centres.

shown in Eq. (4). Then, the image edges are detected (see Fig. 9) with a threshold equal to 0.09, so the values for u_{e1} and u_{e2} are computed and the diameter d_i is found. The diameters detected by the proposed algorithm, exploiting the Eq. (6), are 1.99 mm, 0.53 mm, 1.09 mm, and 3.63 mm, obtaining an error for each wire, respectively of 7.4%, 6.0%, 9.2% and 6.9%. The picking task is implemented with a

Fig. 9. Highlighted wires edges and centres.

Robot Operating System (ROS) network in which the image processing in MATLAB is organized as a service. The two wires of diameters 1.20 mm and 2.15 mm are positioned in the warehouse and the robot moves so that both cameras see both wires and then the image processing service is called. Figure 10 reports the image acquired from the camera 1. The two wires are at the known distances of 112.0 mm and 100.0 mm, respectively, from this camera in order to check the correctness of the results. The cameras acquire a couple of pictures and the aforementioned image elaboration starts. The x and y coordinates of the wires with respect to Σ_c are known *a priori*, the z coordinates estimated from the algorithm are equal to 110.1 mm and 102.9 mm, as expected, corresponding to a percentage error equal to 1.7% and 2.9%, and the detected diameters are 1.10 mm and 1.96 mm, with a mean error of 8.3% and 8.8%, respectively. Figure 11 reports the 3D point cloud segmentation. The user can choose the diameter of the wire to pick: if a wire with the selected diameter is available, the robot aligns the fingers with the x and the y coordinates of the wire, and then the z obtained from the image processing is exploited for the picking. Finally, the tactile sensor checks that the wire is correctly grasped. The flowchart shown in Fig. 12 summarizes the task.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposed a stereo vision system that can be used in those tasks where thin wires are involved to detect some of their features. In particular, the case of position estimation and diameter calculation of DLOs is examined. The vision system consists of two endoscopic cameras mounted on the robot end-effector and, via the robot

Fig. 10. Image acquired from the camera 1.

Fig. 11. 3D point cloud segmentation in the wire picking task.

motion, they are placed in front of the warehouse that stores the wires. To validate the measures obtained from the 3D reconstruction, a picking task is performed. The results are promising, estimating the diameter of wires of less than a millimeter or a few millimeters with an error lower than 10%, while the distance from the cameras is estimated with an error lower than 3%. Future developments include the use of a single camera to implement stereo vision with an *eye-on-hand* approach in order to reduce bulk and to be able to use smaller fingers. Furthermore, the use of cameras with higher resolution will be considered to reduce the diameter estimation error.

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Fig. 12. Wires picking task flowchart.

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